

Model of interaction between the professional education system and the business community

Kasbiy ta'lim tizimi va biznes hamjamiyatining o'zaro ta'siri modeli

Модель взаимодействия системы профессионального образования и бизнес-сообщества

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Annotation: Education is understood as a social institution that performs the functions of preparing and including an individual in various spheres of the life of society, introducing him to the culture of this society. Education is an important social technology, which is both a consequence of the development of society and its condition.

Annotatsiya: Ta'lim deganda shaxsni jamiyat hayotining turli sohalariga tayyorlash va qamrab olish, uni ushbu jamiyat madaniyati bilan tanishtirish funktsiyalarini bajaradigan ijtimoiy institut tushuniladi. Ta'lim muhim ijtimoiy texnologiya bo'lib, u ham jamiyat taraqqiyotining, ham uning holatining natijasidir.

Аннотация: Под образованием понимается социальный институт, выполняющий функции подготовки и включения личности в различные сферы жизни общества, приобщения его к культуре этого общества. Образование является важной

социальной технологией, которая является как следствием развития общества, так и его состояния.

Key words: education, businesses, society, development, career, specialists, community, social institution, infrastructure.

Kalit so'zlar: ta'lim, biznes, jamiyat, rivojlanish, martaba, mutaxassislar, jamoa, ijtimoiy institut, infratuzilma.

Ключевые слова: образование, бизнес, общество, развитие, карьера, специалисты, сообщество, социальный институт, инфраструктура.

The term higher education also refers to the training of highly qualified specialists for the sectors of the economy, science, technology and culture in various types of higher schools, which admit people who have successfully completed secondary general education schools or secondary specialized educational institutions.

Considering the system of vocational education in the context of interaction with society and business, one should understand education as an industry, the results of which can only be seen in the future, and the effect that a person and society receives is difficult to quantify directly.

At the same time, educational services are a product that benefits, first of all, the one who consumes it (the individual and the state), but not directly, but indirectly, through the high quality of the workforce, which means a higher level of income, higher wages. employees and sustainable economic growth, which reveals the investment properties of educational services.

Thus, speaking about the system of interaction between education and the business community, we understand education as a social institution that performs the functions of preparing a qualified workforce in accordance with the requirements of production, the state of science, technology and culture and has the development of society and a competitive economy as its targets.

Based on the analysis of publications of domestic authors on the problems of organizing interaction between the system of vocational education and the labor market, the following main areas of activity can be distinguished:

- organizing monitoring and forecasting the development of regional labor markets, determining the need for personnel, substantiating the volume and structure of their training in the relevant educational institutions;
- creation in the regions of a unified information base on the state of the labor market, the most demanded and promising professions, opportunities for obtaining professional education and employment;
- establishment of partnerships between organizations, enterprises and educational institutions for targeted training and retraining of personnel, as well as the development of a contract system for training young specialists;
- joint activities of employment services and education authorities to bring the structure, volumes and profiles of training in educational institutions in line with the needs of the regional economy;
- Ensuring a high level of training and retraining of personnel in vocational education institutions as the most important condition for increasing the competitiveness and professional mobility of the labor force in the labor market.

The study of the development of the vocational education system made it possible to update a number of problems in the context of organizing a system of interaction between universities and the business community. But it should be noted that a number of problems exist for employers who, with all their desire to cooperate, are not always able to realize their intentions.

The main problem is that many employers do not have detailed plans and programs for the professional and qualification growth of personnel, they prefer to hire ready-made personnel without investing the necessary funds in personnel development. This is also confirmed by the conducted studies - only 15% of enterprises are ready to submit plans for the development of the composition and structure of personnel in accordance with the development of the enterprise itself.

It can be said that the system of vocational education does not have information about how the employer's requirements for the workforce have changed, what the required level of qualifications, knowledge, skills, and skills of a specialist should be from the point of

view of the employer, what requirements he imposes on a graduate of an educational institution. The educational sphere is focused on the needs of the first half of the 90s, and does not take into account the modern needs of enterprises. But in fact, it is quite difficult to get a set of requirements from employers, which is associated with the weakening of the role of the personnel departments of the enterprise, the lack of competent personnel management specialists.

Another problem is the lack of understanding that an enterprise can develop successfully only if the human capital it has at its disposal corresponds in its characteristics to the current and future needs of the enterprise, determined by the development trends of the relevant industry.

In his analysis of the current economic situation in the UK, Michael Porter argues that improving business and national competitiveness is increasingly a collaborative process involving authorities, companies, educational institutions and structures, or, according to M. Porter, collaborative institutions. The competitiveness of a region (city, country) is formed not only by the competitiveness of individual enterprises, but also by the external context in which companies operate and which representatives of the regional economy can change.

Collaboration infrastructure refers to “ways where people and organizations can come to each other to exchange ideas, solve problems and build partnerships”, which implies public-private partnerships, identification of a regional development strategy and a suitable set of “collaboration institutions”.

In an environment where universities and other educational institutions are increasingly contributing to strengthening national and regional competitiveness, and not just playing the traditional role of a training base, it is educational institutions that should become increasingly important as key participants in the regional infrastructure in the process of cooperation.

In the context of these problems, the importance of “partnerships” and the creation of networks of “cooperating organizations” is growing, through which educational institutions and enterprises in the real sector of the economy can openly cooperate to achieve mutual goals. For this activity to be as successful as possible, it is necessary to understand how to

build the so-called "relationships based on mutual influence and learning", where the parties do not just work in parallel, but adapt to each other's needs and take into account the experience of the effective work of their partners.

However, it would be a mistake to focus only on improving "two-way relations" without addressing the growing importance of networks and multi-organizational collaboration in the development of a knowledge-based economy. Businesses, universities, financial institutions, government agencies should engage in such cooperation to support the networked economy.

Thus, in order to improve social dialogue and partnerships in this area, a clear vision of the relevant relationship between the business community and educational institutions is necessary.

In the course of the education reform, a new approach is being generated, when the qualification of a graduate is defined not as recognition of the completed course of study, but as recognition of the result - the acquired body of knowledge and skills to meet the standard qualification requirements for the workplace (business or professional competence of an employee).

The heads of enterprises in the real sector of the economy understand that the "price / quality" ratio segments the educational market both in terms of functional, sectoral, and institutional, territorial, social parameters, therefore, for certain types of supplied "goods", demand in some segments will, as before, exceed the supply, while in a number of others - on the contrary. The "competence-based approach" will not change this situation in the near future, although it may help to even out some obvious imbalances in the future.

Representatives of the business community also understand that from the point of view of society as a whole, the main distinguishing feature of the "educational product" remains its civilizational function (reproduction of culture, morality, scientific and other social progress), but as a buyer of a particular product, the employer is forced to look more utilitarian - costs for the acquisition and operation of the "goods" should pay off and make a profit, contributing to the development of business at the same time on the factors of labor and capital.

An enlarged model of an educational cluster, built on the basis of a system of integration interaction between the system of vocational education and the labor market, is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig.1. Educational cluster model

The mechanism of interaction can be institutionalized, assuming the existence of intermediary structures between the labor markets and vocational education, and non-institutionalized, based on episodic, informal interaction of market entities).

Under the "model of interaction between the labor market and the vocational education system" in this work, we will understand the formed mechanism of interaction between the labor market and the vocational education system, which includes:

- ways of coordinating supply and demand (vacancies) for specialists of one skill level or another;
- ways to harmonize the changing requirements of employers to the competencies of specialists of one or another skill level and educational training trajectories within the framework of the asynchronous education system;

- forms of participation of enterprises-employers and network public organizations in the activities of the vocational education system in order to achieve compliance with the requirements for the qualifications of graduates to the disciplines and levels of curricula;
- information and organizational and technological tools that ensure the functioning of the mechanism of interaction between the labor market and the educational services market.
- management decision support system for the implementation of the interaction mechanism.

The implementation of the presented model is carried out on the basis of a number of organizational mechanisms that require the establishment of a separate structural unit in the university - the Center for Strategic Partnership, i.e. the described model is institutionalized. At the same time, it should be noted that such a mechanism is not hierarchically controlled, it is based on the coordination of interests of all parties - participants in the interaction process, and is based on voluntary strategic cooperation.

The functions of the Center for Strategic Partnership are aimed at achieving the goals mentioned above and allow solving the existing problems of organizing a system of interaction between the university and the business community.

Table 1

Functions of the University Strategic Partnership Center

No	Function	Tasks
1	Financial	Formation of the Endowment Fund
		Implementation of consulting services
		Conclusion of contracts with enterprises for research and development
		Conclusion of contracts for targeted training of specialists
2	Organizational	Creation and maintenance of a database of enterprises and associations (unions, public organizations) - potential partners of the university
		Creation and maintenance of the database of graduates
		Maintenance of the interactive system "Professional" - as an information technology of interaction
3	Innovative	Commercialization of R&D results
4	Research	Labor market monitoring
		Monitoring of the market of educational services

		Creation of Atlases of professions and profессиograms of specialists
		Analysis of demand and employment of graduates
5	Educational	Organization and conduct of advanced training courses
		Organization and conduct of trainings and master classes

The Center for Strategic Partnership can be organized both on the basis of a higher educational institution and at the regional level as a public organization. The option of organizing the Center for Strategic Partnership is selected depending on the specific situation in the region or municipality. If there is a large university or institute in the region, which is a backbone educational core, it is advisable to form a center of strategic partnership on its basis, which will allow optimizing the coordination links of the interaction system. If there are several higher education institutions of equal status and importance in the region, then it will be more effective to organize an independent Center for Strategic Partnership, which, in addition to the goals and functions outlined above, allows to coordinate interests within the system of vocational education at the same level.

Regardless of the chosen option for organizing the Center for Strategic Partnership, it is necessary to build an institutional unit into the existing vocational education management system

Thus, the study of the organizational aspects of the vocational education system and the labor market, a comparative analysis of international and domestic experience in the formation of interaction models, the use of integration theory and a systematic approach made it possible to propose a model of the integration system of interaction between vocational education and the labor market, which implements the coordination of the interests of the participants and is aimed at achievement of socio-economic effects for the economy of the region.

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